

Jeffrey Ede

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EDUCATION

University of Warwick

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Physics:
From Oct 2017 (thesis is finished)

Master of Physics (MPhys) and

Bachelor of Science (BSc) in Physics:

Aug 2013 - Jul 2017, First Class with
Honours

PERSONAL

Date of Birth: 13th Jul 1995

Nationality: English

Salary: Best Offer

Willing to Relocate: Yes

Remote Work: Prefer On-Site

LINKS

arXiv:// [Jeffrey Ede](#)

GitHub:// [Jeffrey Ede](#)

LinkedIn:// [Jeffrey Ede](#)

StackOverflow:// [Jeffrey Ede](#)

INTERESTS

Data curation and processing

Parallel and distributed computing

Automation

Machine learning

SKILLS

Programming

Over 10k lines:

Python • C/C++ • MATLAB • LaTeX

Over 1k lines:

DigitalMicrograph • Java • R

Familiar:

Arduino • LabVIEW • Mathematica •

Verilog • OpenCL • MySQL

Machine Learning

Training:

adversarial • reinforcement • supervised

Architectures:

actor-critic • AE • CNN • DNC •

encoder-decoder • GAN • MLP • RNN •

VAE • VAE-GAN

Miscellaneous:

dataset curation • style transfer • tSNE

SYNOPSIS

I am about to submit my finished doctoral thesis and want to arrange a job as soon as possible. My start date is flexible. I have four years of programming experience and a background in physics, machine learning, and automation.

EXPERIENCE

Researcher – Machine Learning / Electron Microscopy

From Oct 2017 at the University of Warwick

My doctoral thesis titled "[Advances in Electron Microscopy with Deep Learning](#)" was completed under the supervision of [Jeremy Sloan](#). Highlights include:

- Search engines based on variational autoencoders.
- Reinforcement learning to train recurrent neural networks to piecewise adapt sparse scans to specimens for compressed sensing.
- Generative adversarial networks for quantum mechanics and compressed sensing.
- Signal denoising for low electron dose imaging.
- Curation, management, and processing of large new machine learning datasets.

In addition, I was a teaching assistant in undergraduate labs for quantum conduction and electronics experiments.

Summer Internship – Atomic Force Microscopy

Jul - Sep 2017 at the University of Warwick

Programmatic automation of an atomic force microscope, lock-in amplifiers, and superconducting magnets in [Marin Alexe's](#) research group.

Summer Internship – Ultrafast Spectroscopy

Jul - Sep 2015 at the University of Warwick

Programmatic Fourier analysis and wavelet decomposition of broadband optical spectra to determine material properties in [James Lloyd-Hughes'](#) research group.

PUBLICATIONS

- [1] J. M. Ede, "[Review: Deep Learning in Electron Microscopy](#)," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.08328*, 2020.
- [2] J. M. Ede, "[Warwick Electron Microscopy Datasets](#)," *Machine Learning: Science and Technology*, vol. 1, no. 045003, 2020.
- [3] J. M. Ede and R. Beanland, "[Partial Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy with Deep Learning](#)," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2020.
- [4] J. M. Ede and R. Beanland, "[Adaptive Learning Rate Clipping Stabilizes Learning](#)," *Machine Learning: Science and Technology*, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 015011, 2020.
- [5] J. M. Ede and R. Beanland, "[Improving Electron Micrograph Signal-to-Noise with an Atrous Convolutional Encoder-Decoder](#)," *Ultramicroscopy*, vol. 202, pp. 18–25, 2019.
- [6] J. M. Ede, J. J. P. Peters, J. Sloan, and R. Beanland, "[Exit Wavefunction Reconstruction from Single Transmission Electron Micrographs with Deep Learning](#)," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2001.10938*, 2020.
- [7] J. M. Ede, "[Adaptive Partial Scanning Transmission Electron microscopy with Reinforcement Learning](#)," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.02786*, 2020.
- [8] J. M. Ede, "[Deep Learning Supersampled Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy](#)," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.10467*, 2019.